

Analysis of Job Satisfaction and Remuneration on Employee Engagement Crewing at Shipping Line

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Shipping Line, Job Satisfaction, Remuneration, Employee Engagement

Received : 3 September

Revised : 20 September

Accepted: 22 October

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to see the effect between job satisfaction and employee engagement, secondly, to look for the influence between Remuneration and employee engagement, and jointly to see if there is an influence between job satisfaction, remuneration, and employee engagement. This study used a survey method. Therefore, the method used in this study is a quantitative approach with a correlational type of research. The population of this study is crewing domestic route ships at shipping companies in DKI Jakarta, Sample of all 1 converts in domestic route shipping companies as many as 38 people whose working period is over 3 years, using simple regression analysis assisted by SPSS version 21. The variables of Job satisfaction, Remuneration, and Employee Engagement, provide a result of the description and discussion above that job satisfaction does not have a positive and significant influence on job attachment, and remuneration does not have a positive and significant influence on employee attachment. The results of this study are just the beginning because the object used is related to the shipping field and the respondents used are crewing shipping ships in DKI Jakarta, with the sample being a chief officer in shipping companies with domestic route

INTRODUCTION

The shipping industry has an important role in global trade and logistics. Behind every successful sea voyage, there is a dedicated crew, who keep the ship sailing safely and efficiently. The involvement of ship crews in their work is a key factor ensuring operational success in the industry (Exarchopoulos et al., 2018; Wu & Beaverstock, 2013). In this context, we will discuss two important factors that influence employee engagement in the shipping industry, namely job satisfaction and remuneration. Job satisfaction is a measure of the extent to which an employee is satisfied with his job. It covers aspects such as relationships with colleagues, career development opportunities, satisfaction with superiors, and compatibility between abilities and tasks (Burr & Floridi, 2020). In the shipping industry, ship crews face unique challenges such as long travel times, isolation from family, and high work pressure (Jepsen et al., 2015; Paukstat, 2017). Therefore, it is important to understand the level of job satisfaction of ship crews and how it can affect their involvement in carrying out their duties (Cole, 2021).

Employees who are satisfied with their jobs tend to be more motivated and committed to giving their best in their duties. They feel connected to their company's purpose and values, which in turn, can improve the operational efficiency and safety of ships (Svensson et al., 2021). According to (Adeoye & Fields, 2014; Upadhyay, 2009) Remuneration or compensation refers to all forms of remuneration given to employees in exchange for the work they do. This includes salary, benefits, bonuses, and other benefits. In the shipping industry, compensation is often an important factor influencing crew motivation. Employees who feel they are being compensated fairly and proportionately to their duties and responsibilities tend to be more engaged in their work. Good compensation can be an incentive to maintain work quality and minimize crew turnover, which can disrupt the operational sustainability of the ship (Xavier, 2014).

Employee engagement as a measure of the extent to which employees feel connected, committed, and motivated to make their best contribution to their work (Swarnalatha & Prasanna, 2013). In the shipping industry, crew involvement is a key factor for maintaining operational success and safety (Barnett & Pekcan, 2017). The relationship between job satisfaction and remuneration with crew involvement is an important research topic in the context of the shipping industry (Galieriková, 2019). How feelings of job satisfaction and compensation affect crew motivation, and how this influence can be managed to increase their engagement are questions that need to be answered.

Studies from (Sun & Bunchapattanasakda, 2019) say that increased job satisfaction is often associated with increased employee engagement or employee involvement in their work. Employees who are satisfied with their work tend to be more motivated and committed to making a greater contribution in the organization (Vorina et al., 2017). Studies from (Kadir et al., 2019) say Compensation or remuneration is one of the important factors that affect employee motivation. Employees who feel that they are being compensated fairly and according to their contributions tend to be more engaged in their work (Hendriks et al., 2023). Therefore, good remuneration can increase the level of

employee engagement (Cahyanugroho et al., 2016). Employees who feel that they are being paid well and fairly tend to be more satisfied with their work. Conversely, if employees feel that they are not being paid according to their contributions, this can reduce the level of job satisfaction (Zaraket & Saber, 2017). While there has been a lot of research on job satisfaction, remuneration, and employee engagement in a variety of industry contexts, there is a lack of research that focuses on the shipping industry, especially when it comes to ship crew. The industry has unique characteristics, such as long contract terms, travel away from home, and different environmental challenges. Therefore, it is necessary to fill this knowledge gap by understanding how job satisfaction and remuneration contribute to employee engagement in the context of the crew.

Focus on the shipping industry and ship crew in the context of the relationship between job satisfaction, remuneration, and employee engagement. This research will provide valuable insight into how these factors are interconnected in this distinctive industry, and how shipping companies can increase their crew engagement through wise job satisfaction and remuneration management. In addition, the study may also provide new insights into how these factors can be applied in other industries that share similar characteristics in terms of employee engagement. The purpose of this study itself is to see the effect between job satisfaction and employee engagement, secondly looking for the influence between Remuneration and employee engagement and jointly to see if there is an influence between job satisfaction, remuneration and employee engagement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Job Satisfaction

Employee Commitment as a Predictor of Seafarer Retention Using surveys on officers, the study examined the relationship between employee engagement and seafarer safety, performance, and retention. While this does not directly address job satisfaction, it does suggest that employee engagement is an important factor in seafarer retention (Bhattacharya, 2015b). Studies from (Yuen et al., 2018a, 2018b) state that factors affecting job satisfaction and seafarer performance, show that job satisfaction is significantly correlated with job performance, and stress is an important factor affecting job satisfaction.

Seafarers' job satisfaction is related to financial security, leisure time at home, nature and dynamics of work, promotions, salary and benefits, work environment, sense of status and satisfaction with management (McVeigh et al., 2019). Job satisfaction is due to severe or persistent physical factors or psychological or social factors stressors and is also based on a combination of several factors, The majority of factors usually relate to social and psychological problems related to personal and professional life. Employee job satisfaction is important in the work of every professional. A large number of satisfied crews are directly related to lower turnover. Therefore catching Indian seafarers feeling career satisfaction should be a top priority for every employee, Satisfied with work

Sailors are prolific sailors and productive sailors tend to be happy. Motivated and satisfied sailors are more likely to be to participate in relation to maintaining productivity and organizational commitment to satisfaction (Bhattacharya, 2015a).

Employee Engagement

According to (Wahba, 2015) The lack of a generally accepted definition of employee engagement is one of the first challenges found in the literature. If there is no common understanding of employee attachment, it will be very fragmented. The term "employee" is not well defined

Due to the importance of this in today's business organizations, employee engagement has recently become one of the most researched HR topics. Employee performance, engagement, competitive advantage, are just some of the results of organizations that prioritize engagement (Rameshkumar, 2020). Employee engagement is a dynamic term with many factors influencing engagement levels. So, there are many ways to drive engagement, but there is no one-size-fits-all approach for organizations. Pulse surveys that focus on employee engagement or employee satisfaction, for example, are becoming increasingly common over traditional annual surveys. Periodic surveys and more regular employee surveys are common solutions to employee engagement issues identified through extensive research (Garg et al., 2021).

Remuneration

Team-sharing compensation systems are widely used in fishing to overcome moral hazards caused by asymmetric information sharing between capital owners and teams. To perform a basic analysis of such a system, it is important to know how it handles fuel costs (Prellezo & Iriondo, 2016). According to (Guillen & Maynou, 2014) stated regarding remuneration in the marine sector that different crew reward systems can affect fishing objectives and lease distribution in different ways.

The general rules applicable regarding the remuneration of fishery workers are relatively the same from country to country and from time to time. Forms of payment have evolved from non-monetary payments to monetary payments (Matthiasson, 2020).

Hypotheses Development

Relationship Job Satisfaction and Employee Engagement

The relationship between variables will be described from several related studies. The study results from (Ali & Farooqi, 2014) with the aim of knowing the effect of workload on job satisfaction and the effect of job satisfaction on employee performance and commitment and with the result of workload overload that affects job satisfaction, which ultimately affects employee performance and employee attachment.

Studies from (Huang et al., 2016) with the aim of safety climate research related to job satisfaction, commitment, and employee turnover rate, which emphasize the positive impact of safety climate in addition to safety outcomes in general with the results of employee perception research on safety climate related

to employee job satisfaction, commitment and objective turnover rate, which supports the application of social exchange theory. Job satisfaction is also a significant mediator between the safety climate and the two HR outcomes (i.e. engagement and employee turnover).

H1: *Job Satisfaction has positive and significant on Employee Engagement.*

Relationship Remuneration and Employee Engagement

To see the relationship between these two variables, there are several studies that support the same two types of variables, in relation to ship crews it is still rare for this variable to be used, so there are several studies from various fields that are used as a basis. Studies from (Stachowska, 2016) research objectives and by using qualitative methods to introduce the importance of rewards to increase employee engagement, taking into account complex approaches in rewarding employees and research results of comprehensive remuneration models increase employee engagement, guarantee satisfaction and create development opportunities and career opportunities, maintain a balance between work and responsibility Others (work-family life balance), on the other hand, guide the company. development and success and multiply the impact.

Study from (Abror et al., 2020) with the aim of research to examine the relationship between self-efficacy, employee attachment, remuneration, satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and employee loyalty, with the results of the study (1) commitment has a significant effect on satisfaction, (2) commitment is also an important antecedent of lecturer loyalty (3) self-efficacy significantly. affect satisfaction (4) self-efficacy has a significant effect on OCB (5) rewards have a significant effect on satisfaction (6) rewards are also an important antecedent of OCB (7) satisfaction has a significant effect on loyalty and lastly (8) satisfaction has a significant effect on OCB.

H1: *Remuneration has positive and significant on Employee Engagement*

Framework Model

The framework proposed in this study with literature from (Ali & Farooqi, 2014), (Huang et al., 2016), (Stachowska, 2016), and (Abror et al., 2020), here is the framework used in this study.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This study used a survey method. The purpose of the survey method is to collect information about respondents' choices using structured questionnaires (Sekaran, 2010). The methods used are limited to descriptive studies or samples that test previously validated hypotheses (Vogt, 2015). Testing the proposed hypothesis using statistical expressions or structural models suitable for causal analysis. Therefore, the method used in this study is a quantitative approach with a type of correlational research, which is a type of research whose purpose is to find out whether there is a relationship between several variables (Cooper & Schlinder, 2006).

The population of this study is crewing domestic route ships at shipping companies in DKI Jakarta, Sample of all 1 converts in domestic route shipping companies as many as 38 respondent whose working period is over 3 years, using simple regression analysis assisted by SPSS version 21.

RESEARCH RESULT

In the validity test through SPSS V.21 obtained from all statement items given to all respondents totaling 38 respondent filled in through questionnaire sheets and processed data, all statements from job satisfaction variables are declared valid and can be processed further.

Table 1 . Validity Test Job Satisfaction

Statistics		
Job Satisfaction		
N	Valid	38
	Missing	0

In the validity test through SPSS V.21 obtained from all statement items given to all respondents totaling 38 people filled in through questionnaire sheets and processed data, all statements from job satisfaction variables are declared valid and can be processed further.

Table 2.
 Validity Test
 Job_Satisfaction

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	32	1	2.6	2.6
	34	1	2.6	5.3
	37	2	5.3	10.5
	39	2	5.3	15.8
	40	4	10.5	26.3
	41	6	15.8	42.1
	42	1	2.6	44.7
	43	3	7.9	52.6
	44	5	13.2	65.8
	45	5	13.2	78.9
	46	4	10.5	89.5
	47	2	5.3	94.7
	48	1	2.6	97.4
	49	1	2.6	100.0
Total	38	100.0	100.0	

In the frequency test process through SPSS V.21, a standard deviation frequency test was carried out to obtain a percentage of validity and a cumulative percentage stating that the results of the independent variable of job satisfaction were very satisfactory.

Table 3. Validity Test Remuneration

N	Valid	38
	Missing	0

In the validity test through SPSS V.21 obtained from all statement items given to all respondents totaling 38 people filled in through questionnaire sheets and processed data, all statements from remuneration variables are declared valid and can be processed further.

**Table 4. Validity Test
Remuneration**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	28	1	2.6	2.6
	32	2	5.3	7.9
	35	1	2.6	10.5
	37	2	5.3	15.8
	38	1	2.6	18.4
	39	4	10.5	28.9
	40	6	15.8	44.7
	41	1	2.6	47.4
	42	1	2.6	50.0
	43	4	10.5	60.5
	44	4	10.5	71.1
	45	1	2.6	73.7
	46	2	5.3	78.9
	47	3	7.9	86.8
	48	1	2.6	89.5
	49	2	5.3	94.7
	50	2	5.3	100.0
Total	38	100.0	100.0	

In the frequency test process through SPSS V.21, a standard deviation frequency test was carried out to obtain the percentage of validity and cumulative percentage stating that the results of the independent variable remuneration were very satisfactory.

Frequencies Y

Statistics		
Employee Engagement		
N	Valid	38
	Missing	0

In the validity test through SPSS V.21, it was obtained from all statement items given to all respondents totaling 38 people filled in through questionnaire sheets and processed data processing, all statements from the employee engagement variable were declared valid and could be processed further.

Employee Engagement					
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	35	2	5.3	5.3	5.3
	36	1	2.6	2.6	7.9
	38	2	5.3	5.3	13.2
	39	3	7.9	7.9	21.1
	40	5	13.2	13.2	34.2
	42	1	2.6	2.6	36.8
	43	7	18.4	18.4	55.3
	44	4	10.5	10.5	65.8
	45	2	5.3	5.3	71.1
	46	4	10.5	10.5	81.6
	47	5	13.2	13.2	94.7
	49	1	2.6	2.6	97.4
	50	1	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total	38	100.0	100.0		

In the frequency test process through SPSS V.21, a standard deviation frequency test was carried out to obtain a percentage of validity and a cumulative percentage stating that the results of the dependent variable of employee attachment were very satisfactory.

Regression

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.493 ^a	.243	.200	3.392

a. Predictors: (Constant), Remuneration, Job Satisfaction

Based on the model summary table above, the R Square number is 0.493 or (49.3%). This shows that the independent variables of job satisfaction (X1) and remuneration (X2) were able to increase the dependent variable of employee attachment (Y) by 49.3%. While $1 - 49.3 = 50.7\%$ there are several variables or other variables that are not included in this research model.

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	129.601	2	64.800	5.632	.008 ^b
	Residual	402.715	35	11.506		
	Total	532.316	37			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Engagement

b. Predictors: (Constant), Remuneration, Job_Satisfaction

From the data above, $F_{\text{calculate}} = 5.632$, $F_{\text{table}} = 3.25$, $F_{\text{calculate}} > F_{\text{table}}$, then H_0 is rejected meaning that there is a difference in employee attachment between job satisfaction and remuneration or a level of significance of 0.05, Significance of test results $p = (0.000 < 0.05)$, then H_0 rejected means that there is a difference in employee attachment between job satisfaction and remuneration.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.413	8.903		1.507	.141
	Job_Satisfaction	.243	.151	.238	1.605	.118
	Remuneration	.448	.165	.403	2.718	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Employee_Engagement

□

The test results state:

1) First Hypothesis Testing

H_0 : Job satisfaction has no effect on employee performance

H_1 : Job satisfaction affects employee performance

From the results of the analysis, the number of t-values calculated for the variable X_1 is 1.507, with a significance level of 0.118, because the number of significance levels is more < 0.05 ($0.118 > 0.05$), it can be concluded that job satisfaction has no effect on employee attachment. Based on this explanation, H_0 is therefore accepted and rejected H_1 , meaning that job satisfaction has no effect on employee attachment.

2) Second Hypothesis Testing

H_0 : Remuneration has no effect on employee attachment

H_1 : Remuneration affects employee engagement

From the results of the analysis, the number of t-values calculated by the variable X_2 is 2.718, with a significance level of 0.10, because the number of significance levels is more < 0.05 ($0.010 > 0.05$), it can be concluded that remuneration has no effect on employee attachment. Based on this explanation, H_0 is therefore accepted and rejected H_1 , meaning that remuneration has no effect on employee attachment.

1) The effect of job satisfaction on employee attachment.

From hypothesis testing conducted using a partial test (t test), it is known that job satisfaction does not have a positive and significant influence on employee attachment. Based on this explanation, H_0 is therefore rejected and H_1 is accepted, meaning that job satisfaction has no effect on employee attachment.

2) The effect of employee attachment on employee attachment.

From hypothesis testing conducted using a partial test (t test), it is known that remuneration does not have a positive and significant effect on employee attachment. Based on the explanation by therefore H0 is accepted and rejected H1, meaning that employee attachment has no effect on employee attachment.

DISCUSSION

From the results of the above processing of each variable and the relationship between variables, job satisfaction does not have a positive and significant influence on employee attachment, while remuneration does not have a positive and significant influence on employee attachment.

In addition to the real results, from each existing reference there are several other variables that accompany in addition to the three variables in this study.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Research with variables Job satisfaction, Remuneration and Employee Engagement, provides a result from the description and discussion above that job satisfaction does not have a positive and significant influence on job attachment, remuneration does not have a positive and significant influence on employee attachment.

The results of this study are just the beginning, because the object used is related to the shipping field and the respondents used are crewing shipping ships in DKI Jakarta, with the sample being chief officer 1 in shipping companies with domestic route.

FURTHER STUDY

The limitations of this study are only on three variables used, namely job satisfaction, remuneration, and employee engagement, due to the limitations of the researchers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The results of this research are expected to provide benefits for the institutions of each researcher and make a positive contribution to the research treasure, especially in the field of shipping and International Journal of Sustainable Social Science (IJSSS) for publish this article.

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